

Pain and its many faces

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Summary

The work describes the idea of the formation of pain, moreover the pain classification was conducted and various types of pain were enumerated. This work describes also selected forms of acute pain. The variety of measuring pain in paediatric patients was additionally underlined. A quick diagnosis of the pain cause as well as early treatment, influence a significant improvement in the quality of life and self-esteem of the patients who were reported to the Emergency Department. The duties of a doctor, a nurse and a paramedic cover reducing patients' pain. The lack of such activities as well as knowledge of the physiology of the formation of pain will enable the recognition of pain and the usage of appropriate pain treatment methods. Although pain is a negative feeling, it plays an important function in the human organism including warning and protective aspect.

Keywords: pain, suffering, acute pain, chronic pain, morphine, conduction of pain, opioid receptors..

Introduction

Pain is a subjective and unpleasant feeling which is a result of a damaging stimulus or a situation when manifestation of such a stimulus is possible. Patient's individual experiences are very important when it comes to perceiving pain. It may result in different perceptions of pain as well as a complete absence of that symptom. Pain's main function in an organism is to warn and to trigger a protective reaction. A simple example may be pricking a finger with a needle where the consequence is immediate pulling the finger back as a reaction to pain. Pain also forces one to limit physical activity which in turn decreases the risk of making the injury more severe. The term for physiological reception of pain is nociception. However, in clinical practice the unit is suffering as mental reflection of behaviour while in pain [1].

1. Pain creation mechanism

The mechanism of creating pain is nociception. It includes a few stages: transduction, conduction, modulation and perception. Picture number 1 presents this process in a graphical way (Diagram 1).

Transduction

At this stage the energy of the damaging stimulus is converted into an electric impulse. That impulse is conducted by the nerve fibers, situated in peripheral neuron endings. There are two types of nerve fibers responsible for pain conduction: fibers C and type A – δ [2, 3].

The C type fibers are very thin, are susceptible to damage and do not have the neurolemma. Such structure causes the conduction of the stimulus which is very slow. The sensation of spread pain and inability to locate it suggests that the fiber has numerous branches. These fibers react mostly to thermal, chemical and mechanical impulses. In the final segments of these fibers there are various receptors, mostly the opioid ones. This process is meant to activate the receptors and takes a few hours. The A – δ type fibers on the other hand have a neurolemma. They have smaller field of impulse reception which is important in localizing pain. The conduction is much faster which in turn allows the organism to activate the "fight or flight" mechanism. However, they do not have opioid receptors and at their endings there are pain receptors with an active stimulation. The distinguishing features of these fibers suggest a conclusion that it is easier to block out slow pain than to slow down fast pain [4].

Diagram nr 1. *The process of nociception.* Description based on:[2]

Conduction and modulation

In this process the nociceptive information is transferred in the form of an electric impulse to the vertebral ganglion. There the stimulating amino acids such as glutaminian, asparginian and neurokinin are released. They serve as neurotransmitters as well as modulators. They are transported by cells to synapses through separable termination of nociceptor neuron in the posterior horn of the spinal cord. There are several ways of conducting the nociceptive information. The beginning of the way is the hornu posterius and the end is in the upper parts of the central nervous system.

Next these tracts lead to midbrain and medulla oblongata. In that area the descending tract begins. The function of that road is to maintain or block pain in the medulla oblongata. The blocking function of that tract is regulated by the on/off cells. These cells are dependent on the regulation of the opioid system and GABA. When the opioids, which are able to cross the blood-brain barrier, are released, they reach the receptors in the midbrain. The blocking tract gets stimulated and the result is the analgesic effect [5].

Perception

It is the final process of the nonception and it takes place in the cortical centers. According to research stimulating the cortex has a positive influence on memory development pain behaviours [6]. Additionally fear, anxiety and emotions influence the perception of pain. It may also depend on environmental and cultural factors. On that level pain emission is treated using psychotherapy methods, for example treating anxiety or depression [7].

Classification and types of pain

When differentiating pain, it is important to pay attention to the emission duration. Pain lasting shorter than three months is called an acute pain. Pain lasting longer than three months is considered to be chronic pain. The time criterion was established by the International Association for the Study of Pain [8].

Pain can also be divided into groups based on its location:

- Somatic pain involves surface structures such as skin layers, muscles or the bone – joint system.
- Celiac pain concerns internal organs, for example chest pain or abdomen pain.

Acute pain emission manifests as a result of damaging tissues or presence of some disease. If the person suffering from pain does not receive help in the form of pain relief, it will have consequences such as temporarily worse psycho-movement activity which in turn may result in permanent disability or even death. Such pain has a clear reason and because of that it is easy to localize [9].

The degree of pain intensity varies as every patient gathers certain pain experiences during their lifetime which are also dependent on personality and temper. The priority is to remove the reason of pain or – if the former is impossible – to conduct actions reducing the level of pain. Of course each treatment, which usually gives positive effects, should be properly individualised for the particular patient as well as in accordance with the patient's psycho-social needs [10].

Many researchers define chronic pain as pain affliction lasting longer than three months or persists despite the damaged tissues have healed. However, the opinion that

chronic pain is a disease in its own right is equally common. It requires an interdisciplinary therapeutic treatment. Patients who suffer from pain also experience a decline of the quality of life in the form of physiological, psychological and social disorders. It is a fact that the intensity depends on the duration of pain and how severe it is and not on the reasons why it appeared in the first place [11].

In the light of the most recent research, neuropathic pain can be distinguished. It is caused by primary injury of the nervous system. Its appearance is connected with hyperactivity of peripheral or central neurons. This type of pain takes different forms as despite the fact there is the same process responsible for developing it, it also combines the symptoms coming from the autonomic nervous system. The appearance of pain is also connected with the location of the injuries to the system's structures: pressure on the peripheral nerves, injury to the spinal cord or to the brain [12].

Among the most common neuropathic pain syndromes the following can be distinguished:

- root syndrome;
- phantom pain;
- spinal cord pain;
- diabetic neuropathy;
- postherpetic neuralgia.

Selected acute pain syndromes

To the Emergency Department, the most frequently reported patients are those with various pain syndromes caused by injury or diseases associated with internal organs [13].

Post-traumatic pain is an inevitable consequence of every injury, which may cause serious injury. The intensity depends on the extent, severity and the place of the injuries. The informational and warning function of pain is an important element, because it helps in diagnosis and treatment of injuries. Among post-traumatic pain other types can be distinguished: basal pain and pain associated with the performance of therapeutic procedures. Analgesics treatment is a multi-level process which begins at the pre-hospital phase (the place of the accident or during transport to the hospital) and during the early hospital phase- at the Emergency Department [14].

As a result of injury, the most frequent consequence is the damage of the musculoskeletal system which may cause discomfort or pain. In the case of dislocation, a victim feels a sharp pain as a result of the tear of capsular ligament, the displacement of the ends of the bone-building joints or damage to the other components of the joint.

Because of the development of communication, infrastructure and mechanization of work, the injuries or even fractures occur more frequently. The injuries are caused by the breakdown of the bone tissue. The type and strength of injury is important for assessing the type and location of the fracture. Extensive damage to the layers of

skin, muscles, blood vessels together with a severe pain are the main symptoms of open or closed fractures.

An example of another serious injury is an amputation. It's a dangerous injury at different levels of the upper or lower limbs. It is also connected with damage to the nervous-vascular bundle. The pain associated with such pathology is complex, because of the nerves damage.

A common reason for medical emergencies or notification to the ED is sharp pain caused by internal injuries. Among the most characteristic features of pain are its location, severity, and the circumstances of the emergency or radiation. Important elements in the correct diagnosis are the correct description of pain, proper medical interview and an assessment of pain intensity. All these procedures can help in the differentiation of the most common internal causes of acute pain [15].

Chest pain will always cause anxiety and fear. Such an incident must always require rapid differential diagnosis to exclude urgent states or life threatening. These conditions include: myocardial infarction, aortic dissection or pulmonary embolism. You should quickly take the appropriate therapeutic procedures, as well as pain relieving procedures. In myocardial infarction, pulmonary embolism, or mediastinitis, it is recommended to use the opioids - morphine, i.v. [16].

Pain may also result from diseases of the abdominal cavity, which is in the form of short-term incident that step down after a time. At the same time abdominal pain may be a symptom of a very serious disease, ie. Peritonitis or perforation of the gastrointestinal tract. In the literature such acute conditions are called "acute abdomen" and require immediate surgical intervention [17]. With the activation of the autonomic nervous system- visceral pain is formed and with the activation of the somatic nervous system - somatic pain is formed. The first of the enumerated forms of pain can be caused by a sudden increase in voltage, smooth muscle contraction or an increase in voltage of internal organs bags. It's hard to locate the focal pain of short duration which steps down after changing the position or changing movement. As a result of irritation of sensory nerves of peritoneum, mesentery or abdominal wall may form somatic pain. During the medical interview the patient easily localises the place of focal pain which can step down at rest or immobility [18].

It is worth paying attention to the diversity of treatment of pain in case of children. In paediatric patients under the age of 3, it is recommended to use behavioural scales, which determine the pain of the change in the child's behaviour. For example: FLACC, CRIES and COMFORT [19]. The pain scales should be mentioned in adults. The scales undergo some modifications, eg. Rock VAS modified illustrations of happy or sad faces which are intended to reflect the intensity of pain [20]. A typical rock Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale, rearranges Figure 1.4. is posted below (Figure 1.4). A simple scale is also

Finger Span Scale, which is intended to show the pain on the basis of the fingers. This method presents posted (Figure 1.5).

Pain treatment in paediatrics

Children belong to a specific group of patients and often are a challenge for health and safety personnel. The problem is noticeable in the process of diagnosis and treatment. This is due to the overall behaviour of children with heterogeneous fear symptoms. Pain for the child is a subjective sensation, manifested in a variety of behaviours, not only related to the disease process but also a psycho - social factor. Many times the symptoms of the children pain were neglected. It was believed that the child feels the pain instead of fear or loneliness, or lack of proper care. The authors of many medical publications show that pain in a young child is to relieve less effectively than in case of an adult. Researchers also pay attention to the fact that most susceptible to pain are newborns. The lack of appropriate standards of knowledge as well as different individual development of paediatric patients is affected by the lack of use of opioid drugs for pain [22]

Pain treatment in young children is effective if an adequate assessment is performed earlier. In order to classify

pain reactions properly, you need to make an accurate quantitative and qualitative measurement. When measuring the pain you have to take into account such factors as: psychological aspect, previous experience of pain, the attitude of parents and the external environment. In infants and newborns, pain is assessed on the basis of: measuring the heart rate, respiratory rate, elevated blood pressure and accelerated gastrointestinal peristalsis. Additionally, you can perform the observation of tears, anxiety and facial expression [23]

Acute pain relief in newborn and premature infants is problematic

for doctors and medical staff. The smallest interventions, like the establishment of the intravenous cannula or blood sampling causes great suffering in children and should also be adequately mitigated. In contrast, in reducing severe pain in newborns the best choice is morphine. It is mainly used in newborns artificially ventilated, because of the possibility of respiratory depression. The advised dose is 5 – 10 µg/kg mc./h.

From the previously conducted research, concerning the pain treatment in the youngest patients, it can be assumed that post-traumatic pain is treated too late and inadequately.

Figure 1.4. The example of the scale: Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale. Based on [21].

Figure 1.5. Finger Span Scale Method. Based on: A. low pain intensity B. the pain of medium intensity C. high pain intensity.

This kind of pain teaches the child to avoid the factors causing such suffering. To the most common injuries in children are injuries caused by the traffic accident, broken bones and burns. The priority of procedure at the place of accident is interviewing and appropriately conducted physical research. Pharmacology is limited to two opioids - morphine and tramadol. The dose of the drugs is dependent on the age and weight of young patients, the best drug administration is by intravenous or intramuscular route. The amount of the dose and route of administration should be recorded in the patient's card or transfer the patient by a team of Emergency Medical Services. The pain caused by the fracture or dislocation may be resistant to the given drugs, and an effective method may be the immobilization and elevation of the limb. In hospital proceedings the therapy with opioids can be continued, if the pain persists and there is no definitive medical diagnosis. An important action is a constant monitoring of vital signs of the patient, especially in terms of respiratory and circulatory system.

Summary

There are many definitions of pain. The most common association of pain is a very subjective and unpleasant feeling. The biological process of the pain formation is nociception, which consists of different stages such as transduction, conduction, modulation and perception. Tissue damage causes changes into an energetic impulse, stimulating nerve fibres, it is a transduction stage. In conduction and modulation the impulse reaches the spinal cord and then the hypothalamus. The impulse reaches centres of the cerebral cortex, where the perception takes place.

The kind of the pain depends on its lasting. Acute pain lasts less than 3 months, whereas chronic pain lasts more than 3 months. Another classification is connected with the pain localisation, somatic pain derived from superficial structures and visceral pain associated with

internal organs. In the literature we can find a variety of pain syndromes that is a challenge for today's medicine. For this purpose the scale was established in order to measure the intensity of pain. This particular type of scales is used in paediatric patients.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.